

EMPLOYEES AND MIDDLE-LEVEL ADMINISTRATORS' WORK ENVIRONMENT AND WORK ENGAGEMENT AT PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN SULU

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study describes the extent of work environment and work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year of 2021-2022. This study reveals the following findings: 1) Out of 190 respondents, almost three-fourth have permanent work status, and almost one-half have Bachelor's degree. 2) Sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment in terms of egoistic, deontological and utilitarian are rated as "Agree" and interpreted as "High Tendency". 3) Sub-categories subsumed under work engagement in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption are rated as "Agree" and interpreted as "High Tendency". 4) No significant difference in the extent of ethical work environment of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of egoistic, deontological, and utilitarian when data are categorized according to length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment. 5) No significant difference in the extent of work engagement of public HEIs in Sulu in the context of vigor, dedication, and absorption when data are categorized according to length of service, and status of appointment. However, significant difference exists when are categorized in terms of educational attainment. Respondents with Master's degree have better ways of perceiving the extent of work engagement in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption. 6) Generally, there is a high positive correlation among the extent of the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment (egoistic, deontological, and utilitarian) and work engagement (vigor, dedication, and absorption) of public HEIs in Sulu. With high correlation between ethical work environment and work engagement, this particular study tends to support the theoretical models proposed by Rothman (2017) Ethical Philosophical Constructs and Bakker's (2011) Work Engagement Model.

Keywords: *Ethical Behavior, work environment, work engagement, professional ethics, public higher education institutions*

INTRODUCTION

In today's work environment, administrators are inevitable to public scrutiny. Public administrators have been shrouded by social issues, albeit morality, work ethics and work engagement.

Organizational work ethics, especially practiced by higher education managers, concern both the general public and academic community. As a result, attention has increased on scrutinizing educators' development of moral reasoning. Past research on individual and professional ethics, as well as the theoretical models that attempt to explain academic decision behavior, indicate that organizational-level variables have a significant impact on individual decisions. Since education managers' decisions impact organizational goals via organizational ethical behavior and work engagement, this researcher wishes to determine the extent of environment and work engagement of middle education managers of higher education institutions.

Ethical work environment has been defined as "perceptions of what constitutes ethically correct behavior and how ethical issues should be handled in the organization" (Peterson, 2002, p. 50 in Baskin et al., 2016). Thus, public higher education institutions in the Philippines are mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to promulgate and implement their operation manuals that should be based, among others, on established ethical standards for public officials and employees.

However, gap seems to have been existed for quite a time now. That is, based on Keenan (2015) analysis of the ethics literature in higher education has reported ethical transgressions in higher education institutions from the late 1980s until 2015, involving administrators and faculty. Ethical work environment in an organization has been impacting the ethical behavior; that is work engagement of the employees within that organization (Rothman, 2017).

In so doing, the literature has also shown that ethical issues in higher education receive little attention. According to Robinson and Moulton (2005 in Rothman, 2017), ethical issues in higher education receive little publicity compared to ethical issues in business, politics, and medicine. Robinson & Moulton (2005) claimed that serious study of ethical issues in higher education has largely been ignored.

Consequently, ethical transgressions can be traced back to the influence of ethical climates (Arnaud, 2010 in Rothman, 2017). The literature indicates that there is a link between the perceived ethical work environment and the ethical behavior or work engagement of an employee. More specifically, ethical climate can be a predictor of the ethical behavior of the employees. Cullen, Victor, and Stephens (1989 in Rothman, 2017) posited that identifying the prevailing ethical climate of an organization constitutes the first crucial step toward creating a climate that is appropriate and effective.

Martin and Cullen (2006 in Rothman, 2017) encouraged future research on ethical climate in various types of organizations. Al-Omari (2012 in Rothman, 2017) opined that there were limited studies of ethical climate in higher education institution, which

prompted his study of the ethical climate in a higher education institution with a focus on the faculty members' perception of the prevailing ethical climate at the university. Al-Omari's primary objective for his study was to obtain empirical data of the perceived ethical climate of the faculty and to use the results to support the development of ethical training and professional development programs to help improve the ethical climate at the studied university.

The literature shows that ethical behavior is linked to the perceived ethical climate of employees, and ethical climate can be a predictor of ethical behavior which is akin to work engagement (Simha & Cullen, 2011 in Rothman, 2017). This fact, coupled with the continual ethical transgressions involving higher education institutions, support the significance of measuring and predicting ethical work environment and work engagement in higher education institutions. Studying these constructs can serve as an effective strategy for the higher education middle managers to better manage the ethical work behavior of their employees. In addition, there is a need to further explore ethics and work engagement in higher education institutions due to the limited research. Specifically, the Keenan (2015) study of higher education institution concluded that ethical behavior is a problem that receives little attention.

Therefore, owing to the compelling reasons aforementioned above, and the need to investigate the prevailing ethics of work environment that which assumed to affect the work engagement of government employees, this study was conducted in order to gather empirical data as bases for the confirmation or denial of the abovementioned claims.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent of work environment and work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year of 2021-2022. More specifically, this research answered each of the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of employees and middle-level administrators of HEIs in Sulu in terms of:
 - 1.1 Length of service;
 - 1.2 Status of appointment; and
 - 1.3 Educational attainment?
2. What is the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of:
 - 2.1 Egoistic ethical behavior;
 - 2.2 Deontological Ethical behavior; and
 - 2.3 Utilitarian Ethical behavior?
3. What is the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of:
 - 3.1 Vigor;
 - 3.2 Dedication; and
 - 3.3 Absorption?

4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to:

- 4.1 Length of service;
- 4.2 Status of appointment; and
- 4.3 Educational attainment?

5. Is there a significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to:

- 5.1 Length of service;
- 5.2 Status of appointment; and
- 5.3 Educational attainment?

6. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design method was employed in this study. According to Bless and Higson-Smith, a research design as “a program that guides a researcher in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts.” (1995:63). Thus, this study purported to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover significant differences and relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge or phenomenon of employees and middle-level administrators of public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sulu. In addition, this study was conducted among public HEIs in Sulu during the Academic Year 2021-2022. These public HEIs are located in the province of Sulu that are under the direct supervision of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). The respondents of this study were the 190 employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu who are currently employed during this Academic Year 2021-2022 regardless of their academic ranks. For the sampling design, a non-probability sampling design through purposive sampling method was employed in this study. The use of purposive sampling in this study was to ensure the proper representation of gender, age, civil status, length of service, status of appointment and educational attainment. A permit to administer the questionnaire was secured from the Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies, the Chancellor/President/Superintendent of HEIs in Sulu; and the researcher launched and administered the questionnaires personally as well as the retrieval. Moreover, a survey questionnaire was the main instrument employed to gather data on the extent of ethical work environment and work engagement among employees of HEIs in Sulu. Work Environment questionnaire was adapted and patterned with slight modification from Rothman, Phillip (2017) Ethical Climate Questionnaire which was based on Al-Omari (2012). This questionnaire has the following sub-categories, namely: Egoism (8 items), Deontological (8 items), and Utilitarian (8 items). On the other hand, the work engagement questionnaire was adapted and patterned with some modification from Bay, Amelia B. et al. (2014). It has the following sub-categories, such as Vigor (6 items), Dedication (5 items), and Absorption (6 items). However, to suit for the usability in the local setting, slight modifications were made and these were subjected to

the perusal of at least two experts from the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of Sulu State College. Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were appropriately employed in the treatment of data gathered for this study, namely:

- 1) For research problem number one 1, frequency counts and percentage were employed to determine the profile of employees and middle-level administrators of HEIs in Sulu;
- 2) For research problem number two 2, mean and standard deviation were employed to determine the extent of the dimensions of work environment;
- 3) For research problem number two 3, mean and standard deviation were employed to determine the extent of the dimensions of work engagement;
- 4) For research problem number 4, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of the dimensions of work environment when data are grouped according to length of service, status of appointment and educational attainment.
- 5) For research problem number 4, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of the dimensions of work engagement when data are grouped according to length of service, status of appointment and educational attainment.
- 6) For research question number 6, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed to determine the degree of correlation between work environment and work engagement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that which correspond to each of the research questions:

Table 1.1 Socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of length of service

Length of Service	Number of Respondents	Percent
5 years & below	59	31.1%
6-15 years	60	31.6%
16-25 years	41	21.6%
26 years & above	30	15.8%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.1 presents the socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of length of service. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 59 (31.1%) have 5 years & below, 60 (31.6%) have 6-15 years, 41 (21.6%) have 16-25 years, and 30 (15.8%) have 26 year & above. In this study, this means that more than one-half of the respondents are within the 15 years of work

experience. This result implies that majority of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu involved in this study are in the evolving/ascending stage of years of experience with regard to their office and school works.

Table 1.2 Socio-demographic profile of employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of status of appointment

Status of Appointment	Number of Employees	Percent
Permanent	120	63.2%
Temporary	15	7.9%
Contractual	55	28.9%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.2 shows the socio-demographic profile of employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of in terms of status of appointment. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 120 (63.2%) are permanent, 15 (7.9%) are temporary, and 55 (28.9%) are contractual. In this study, this means that almost three-fourth respondents are permanent and the other portion are contractual. This result implies that, the total work force of public HEIs in Sulu constitutes almost by permanent employees.

Table 1.3 Socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Employees	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	31	16.3%
Bachelor's with MA units	61	32.1%
Master's Degree	54	28.4%
Master's degree with doctoral units	32	16.8%
Doctoral degree	12	6.3%
Total	190	100%

Table 1.3 presents the socio-demographic profile of the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of educational attainment. This table reveals that out of 190 respondents, 31 (16.3%) have Bachelor's degree, 61 (32.1) have Bachelor's degree with MA units, 54 (28.4%) have Master's degree, 32 (16.8%) have Master's degree with doctoral units, and only 12 (6.3%) have Doctorate degree. In this study, this means that there are almost one-half of the respondents have Bachelor's degree. This result implies that, the trend of academic preparation of the work force

among the public HEIs in Sulu is concentrated more on basic employment qualification which is at least Master's degree or Bachelor's degree for exigency on service.

Table 2.1 Depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Egoistic ethical behavior

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	In this college, people are out mostly for themselves	3.1632	1.06394	Neutral
2	People are expected to further the college's interest, regardless of the consequences	3.5842	.90896	Agree
3	There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this college	3.2263	1.23714	Neutral
4	Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the college's interests	3.4579	1.04188	Agree
5	In this college, people protect their own interest above other considerations	3.2947	1.18074	Neutral
6	People are concerned with the college's interests	4.0579	.69146	Agree
7	Decisions are primarily viewed in terms of contribution to profit	3.6158	.85124	Agree
8	People in this college are very concerned about what is best for themselves	3.7526	1.02191	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.5191	.69867	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 2.1 depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Egoistic ethical behavior. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 3.5191 with standard deviation of .69867 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents perceive that there is a high tendency for the employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to perceive that the organization generally promotes self-interested decisions at the expense of others wherein decision comes directly from the individual who ignores the needs or interests of others.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “People are expected to further the college's interest, regardless of the consequences”, “Work is considered sub-standard only when it hurts the college's interests”, “People are concerned with the college's interests”, “Decisions are primarily viewed in terms of contribution to profit”, and “People in this college are very concerned about what is best for themselves”.

Notably, respondents ranked with “Neutral” the following items: “In this college, people are out mostly for themselves”, “There is no room for one's own personal morals or ethics in this college”, and “In this college, people protect their own interest above other considerations”.

Table 2.2 Depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Deontological ethical behavior

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	It is very important to follow strictly the college's rules and policies	4.5368	.62251	Strongly Agree
2	The first consideration in a decision is whether the decision violates a law	4.1211	.81720	Agree
3	People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations	4.1579	.68723	Agree
4	Everyone is expected to stick by college's rules and policies	4.3000	.62530	Agree
5	Successful people in this college go by the book	3.7211	1.0137	Agree
6	In this college, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards	4.2421	.67008	Agree
7	Successful people in this college strictly obey the college's policies	4.1684	.71496	Agree
8	In this college, the law or ethical code of their profession is the major consideration	4.2895	.66300	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.1921	.43504	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 2.2 depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Deontological ethical behavior. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 4.1921 with standard deviation of .43504 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents perceive that there is a high tendency for the employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to perceive that certain actions of employees at public higher education institutions in Sulu are intrinsically right or wrong, because a person makes an ethical decision based on what is right, following moral rules. Their perspectives center on the actions of individual person and his or her moral obligation and responsibility to do what is right. They also believe that this ethical climate focuses on the behaviors guided by

principle, rules, laws, and codes, which promote decisions and actions for the good of others.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “The first consideration in a decision is whether the decision violates a law”, “People are expected to comply with the law and professional standards over and above other considerations”, “Everyone is expected to stick by college’s rules and policies”, “Successful people in this college go by the book”, and “In this college, people are expected to strictly follow legal or professional standards”.

Notably, respondents ranked with “Strongly Agree” the following item: “It is very important to follow strictly the college’s rules and policies”.

Table 2.3 Depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of utilitarian ethical behavior

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	In this college, people look out for each other's good	4.1316	.79586	Agree
2	The most important concern in this college is each person's sense of what is right and wrong	4.1474	.76246	Agree
3	In this college, our major concern is always what is best for the other person	3.9789	.84175	Agree
4	Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the college	4.2947	.67257	Agree
5	It is expected that you will always do what is right for the students and the public	4.4105	.65860	Agree
6	People are very concerned about what is generally best for employees of the college	4.2368	.67590	Agree
7	What is best for each individual is a primary concern for this college	4.1526	.70738	Agree
8	The effect of decisions on the students and the public are a primary concern in this college	4.1632	.73442	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.1895	.53386	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 2.3 depicts the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Utilitarian ethical behavior. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 4.1895 with standard deviation of .53386 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents have high tendency to believe that employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to have ethical perspectives where employees see their organization as having a vested

interest in the well-being of others. They also hold-on in their expectations that each employee is concerned for the well-being of the other employees.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “In this college, people look out for each other's good”, “The most important concern in this college is each person's sense of what is right and wrong”, “In this college, our major concern is always what is best for the other person”, “Our major consideration is what is best for everyone in the college”, and “It is expected that you will always do what is right for the students and the public”.

Table 3.1 Depicts the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of vigor

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	At my work, I feel bursting with energy.	3.9316	.82331	Agree
2	At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	4.1421	.73161	Agree
3	When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work.	4.1789	.67423	Agree
4	I can continue working for very long periods at a time.	4.1053	.71970	Agree
5	At my job, I am very resilient, mentally.	4.1842	.69978	Agree
6	At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well.	4.0316	.78279	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.0956	.53321	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 3.1 depicts the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Vigor. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 4.0956 with standard deviation of .53321 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents have high tendency to believe that employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to have high spirit and energy levels and mental endurance at work. It is also believed these employees have high tendency to be resilient, mentally alert and persevere even when things do not go well.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “At my work, I feel bursting with energy”, “At my job, I feel strong and vigorous”, “When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work”, “I can continue working for very long periods at a time”, and “At my job, I am very resilient, mentally”.

Table 3.2 Extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Dedication

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	4.2842	.70768	Agree
2	I am enthusiastic about my job.	4.3526	.65616	Agree
3	My job inspires me.	4.4632	.65563	Agree
4	I am proud on the work that I do.	4.4684	.65591	Agree
5	To me, my job is challenging.	4.3947	.65625	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.3926	.58278	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 3.2 depicts the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Dedication. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 4.3926 with standard deviation of .58278 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents have high tendency to believe that employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to have strong involvement in work and feel important, enthusiastic and challenged. They also highly believe that the employees work with full of meaning and purpose and being enthusiastic about their jobs.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose”, “I am enthusiastic about my job”, “My job inspires me”, “I am proud on the work that I do”, and “To me, my job is challenging”.

Table 3.3 Extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Absorption.

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Time flies when I'm working.	4.3632	.68213	Agree
2	When I am working, I forget everything else around me.	4.0684	.81685	Agree
3	I feel happy when I am working intensely.	4.3368	.67629	Agree
4	I am immersed in my work.	4.2158	.67515	Agree
5	I get carried away when I'm working.	4.0895	.84665	Agree
6	It is difficult to detach myself from my job.	4.0474	.84382	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.1868	.59666	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree (Very High Tendency); (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree (High Tendency); (3) 2.50- 3.49=Neutral (Moderate Tendency); (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree (Low Tendency); (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree (Very Low Tendency)

Table 3.3 depicts the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) in the context of Absorption. It can be gleaned from this table that respondents have total weighted mean score of 4.1868 with standard deviation of .59666 which is rated as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Tendency”. This result indicates that respondents have high tendency to believe that employees of public higher education institutions in Sulu to be highly concentrated, excited and engrossed a work as time passes. They also believe that these employees are immersed or absorbed when working, forget everything else around them, and feel happy when they are working intensely.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “Time flies when I’m working”, “When I am working, I forget everything else around me”, “I feel happy when I am working intensely”, “I am immersed in my work”, and “I get carried away when I’m working”.

Table 4.1 Differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Egoistic Ethical Behavior	Between	6.541	3	2.180	4.731*	.003	Significant
	Within Groups	85.718	186	.461			
	Total	92.259	189				
Deontological Ethical Behavior	Between	.427	3	.142	.750	.524	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.342	186	.190			
	Total	35.769	189				
Utilitarian Ethical Behavior	Between	.370	3	.123	.429	.732	Not Significant
	Within Groups	53.496	186	.288			
	Total	53.866	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 4.1 presents the differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table that except for Egoistic Ethical Behavior, the F-values and Probability Values of all of the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally though respondents differ in their length of service, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of ethical work environment. This result implies that an employee who has been in service for 26 years & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of ethical work environment than other employees who have been serving in colleges/universities for 5 years & below, 6-15 years, and 16-25 years, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that employees and middle level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu, though differ in the number of years they been serving in public colleges/universities, generally have the same fashion of perceiving the ways how their schools/universities give priorities to employee rights, fair procedures, and equity in pay and promotion, and that promote tolerance, compassion, loyalty and honesty in the treatment of clientele and employees.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant influence in the ways how employees of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of ethical work environment. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to length of service” is accepted.

Table 4.2 Differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to status of appointment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Egoistic Ethical Behavior	Between	7.648	2	3.824	8.451*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	84.611	187	.452			
	Total	92.259	189				
Deontological Ethical Behavior	Between	.372	2	.186	.982	.376	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.398	187	.189			
	Total	35.769	189				
Utilitarian Ethical Behavior	Between	.319	2	.159	.557	.574	Not Significant
	Within Groups	53.548	187	.286			
	Total	53.866	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 4.2 presents the differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to status of appointment. It can be gleaned from this table that except for Egoistic Ethical Behavior, the F-values and Probability Values of all of the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally though respondents differ in their status of appointment, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of ethical work environment. This result implies that an employee who has permanent appointment may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of ethical work environment than other employees who have temporary and contractual status, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that employees and middle level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu, though differ in appointment status, generally have the same fashion of perceiving the ways how their schools/universities give priorities to employee rights, fair procedures, and equity in pay and promotion, and that promote tolerance, compassion, loyalty and honesty in the treatment of clientele and employees.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable status of appointment has no significant influence in the ways how employees of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of ethical work environment. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to status of appointment” is accepted.

Table 4.3 Differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Egoistic Ethical Behavior	Between	17.399	4	4.350	10.749	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	74.860	185	.405			
	Total	92.259	189				
Deontological Ethical Behavior	Between	1.708	4	.427	2.319	.059	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.061	185	.184			
	Total	35.769	189				
Utilitarian Ethical Behavior	Between	.985	4	.246	.861	.488	Not Significant
	Within Groups	52.882	185	.286			
	Total	53.866	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 4.3 presents the differences in the extent of ethical work environment of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that except for Egoistic Ethical Behavior, the F-values and Probability Values of all of the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally though respondents differ in their educational attainment, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of ethical work environment. This result implies that an employee who has doctorate degree may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of ethical work environment than other employees who have Bachelor’s degree, Bachelor’s degree with MA units, Master’s degree, and Master’s degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that employees and middle level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu, though differ in educational attainment, generally have the same fashion of perceiving the ways how their schools/universities give priorities to employee rights, fair procedures, and equity in pay and promotion, and that promote tolerance, compassion, loyalty and honesty in the treatment of clientele and employees.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant influence in the ways how employees of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of ethical work environment. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical work environment of employees and middle-level

administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to educational attainment” is accepted.

Table 5.1 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Between Groups	.846	3	.282	.991	.398	Not Significant
	Within Groups	52.890	186	.284			
	Total	53.735	189				
Dedication	Between Groups	.989	3	.330	.970	.408	Not Significant
	Within Groups	63.201	186	.340			
	Total	64.190	189				
Absorption	Between Groups	2.529	3	.843	2.421	.067	Not Significant
	Within Groups	64.755	186	.348			
	Total	67.284	189				

**Significant at alpha 0.05*

Table 5.1 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under work engagement are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although respondents differ in their length of service, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of work engagement prevailing among the public HEIs. This result implies that, for an employee to have been in service for 26 years & above, may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of work engagement than other respondents who have working for 5 years & below, 6-15 years, and 16-25 years, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that regardless of being new or old, employees of HEIs in Sulu have similar ways of perceiving the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level

administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to length of service” is accepted.

Table 5.2 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to status of appointment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Between	2.252	2	1.126	4.089*	.018	Significant
	Within Groups	51.484	187	.275			
	Total	53.735	189				
Dedication	Between	1.118	2	.559	1.657	.194	Not Significant
	Within Groups	63.072	187	.337			
	Total	64.190	189				
Absorption	Between	.132	2	.066	.184	.832	Not Significant
	Within Groups	67.152	187	.359			
	Total	67.284	189				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 5.2 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to status of appointment. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under work engagement are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although respondents differ in their appointment status, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of work engagement prevailing in their respective public HEIs. This result implies that, for an employee to have permanent work status may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of work engagement than other respondents who have temporary and contractual appointment, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that regardless of permanent or temporary, employees of HEIs in Sulu have similar ways of perceiving the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable status of appointment has no significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to status of appointment” is accepted.

Table 5.3 Differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Vigor	Between	3.961	4	.990	3.681*	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	49.774	185	.269			
	Total	53.735	189				
Dedication	Between	4.810	4	1.202	3.746*	.006	Significant
	Within Groups	59.380	185	.321			
	Total	64.190	189				
Absorption	Between	3.995	4	.999	2.919*	.023	Significant
	Within Groups	63.289	185	.342			
	Total	67.284	189				

**Significant at alpha 0.05*

Table 5.6 presents the differences in the extent of work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under work engagement are indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, although respondents differ in their educational attainment, generally they really differ in their perceptions toward the extent of work engagement prevailing in their respective public HEIs. This result implies that, for an employee to have doctorate degree may probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of work engagement than other respondents who have Bachelor's degree, Bachelor's degree with MA units, Master's degree, and Master's degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that employees of HEIs in Sulu with levels of educational background indeed differ in ways how they perceive the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Also, they have similar judgment on how HEIs employees care about their work and about the performance, and feel that their efforts make a difference.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has indeed significant influence in the ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu perceive the extent of work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the work engagement of employees and middle-level administrators of public higher education institutions (HEIs) when data are classified according to educational attainment" is rejected.

Table 5.3.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the work engagement among employees and middle-level administrators on public HEIs in Sulu in terms of Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption when data are categorized according to educational attainment.

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Educational Attainment	(J) Grouping by Educational Attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Vigor	Master's degree	Bachelor's degree	.27718	.11688	.234
		Bachelor' degree w/ MA units	.31755*	.09692	.033
		Master's degree w/ doctoral units	.36169*	.11572	.048
		Doctorate degree	.17593	.16554	.889
Dedication	Master's degree	Bachelor's degree	.42342*	.12766	.030
		Bachelor' degree w/ MA units	.02247	.10586	1.000
		Master's degree w/ doctoral units	.12523	.12639	.912
		Doctorate degree	-.13519	.18081	.967
Absorption	Master's degree	Bachelor's degree	.43100*	.13180	.033
		Bachelor' degree w/ MA units	.22723	.10929	.367
		Master's degree w/ doctoral units	.15799	.13048	.832
		Doctorate degree	.06944	.18667	.998

**The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level*

Post Hoc Analysis using Scheffe's Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to educational attainment to have different levels of mean in areas subsumed under the work engagement as perceived by employees and idle-level administrators of public higher education institutions in Sulu.

The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 5.6.1 indicates that the difference in the means of the Vigor, Dedication and Absorption are obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

- a) **On Sub-category Vigor:** It shows that Master's Degree group of respondents obtained the mean difference of .36169* with Standard Error of .11572 and *p* value of .048 which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over Master's Degree with doctoral units. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of perceiving the work engagement in terms of Vigor among employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu than those with Master's degree.
- b) **On Sub-category Dedication:** It shows that Master's Degree group of respondents obtained the mean difference of .42342* with Standard Error of

.12766 and p value of .030 which is significant at alpha=.05 over Bachelor's Degree. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of perceiving the work engagement in terms of Dedication among employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu than those with Master's degree.

- c) **On Sub-category Absorption:** It shows that Master's Degree group of respondents obtained the mean difference of .43100* with Standard Error of .13180 and p=value of .033 which is significant at alpha=.05 over Bachelor's Degree. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of perceiving the work engagement in terms of Absorption among employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu than those with Master's Degree.

Table 6. Correlation between the extent of sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement among employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Egoistic Work Environment	Deontological	.427**	.000	190	Moderate
	Utilitarian	.237**	.001	190	Moderate
	Vigor	.348**	.000	190	Moderate
	Dedication	.014	.845	190	Nearly Zero
	Absorption	.271**	.000	190	Low
Deontological Work Environment	Utilitarian	.632**	.000	190	High
	Vigor	.503**	.000	190	High
	Dedication	.428**	.000	190	Moderate
	Absorption	.484**	.000	190	Moderate
Utilitarian Work Environment	Vigor	.411**	.000	190	Moderate
	Dedication	.442**	.000	190	Moderate
	Absorption	.427**	.000	190	Moderate
Vigor	Dedication	.589**	.000	190	High
	Absorption	.666**	.000	190	High
Dedication	Absorption	.668**	.000	190	High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Table 6 illustrates the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Ethical Work Environment (Egoistic ethical behavior, Deontological Ethical behavior, and Utilitarian Ethical behavior) and Work Engagement (Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption) among employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu.

Specifically, the degrees of correlations among the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement are as follows:

- 1) Low positive correlation between Egoistic ethical behavior AND Deontological Ethical behavior, Utilitarian Ethical behavior, Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption;
- 2) High correlation between Deontological Ethical behavior AND Utilitarian Ethical behavior, Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption;
- 3) Moderate positive correlation between Utilitarian Ethical behavior AND Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption;
- 4) High positive correlation between Vigor AND Dedication, and Absorption;
- 5) High positive correlation between Dedication AND Absorption.

These results indicate that the employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu who generally perceived the extent of ethical work environment in terms of Egoistic, Deontological and Utilitarian as “Agree” or “High Tendency” are most probably the same group of employees and middle-level administrators who perceived the work environment in terms of Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption as “Agree” or “High Tendency”.

Meanwhile, it is safe to say that, generally the extent of sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement are highly correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement” is rejected.

Conclusions

This study concludes that:

- 1) There is sufficient representation of employees and middle-level of public HEIs in Sulu in terms of length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment.
- 2) On the average, employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu have high tendency of providing priority to employee rights, fair procedures, and equity in pay and promotion, and that promote tolerance, compassion, loyalty and honesty in the treatment of clienteles and employees.
- 3) On the average, employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs in Sulu have high tendency of ensuring their workers with high level of enthusiasm and dedication toward their job.
- 4) Variables length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment do not influence on ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs perceive the extent of ethical work environment.
- 5) Except for educational attainment, variables length of service, and status of appointment do not influence on ways how employees and middle-level administrators of public HEIs perceive the extent of work engagement.
- 6) Sub-categories subsumed under ethical work environment and work engagement are highly correlated.
- 7) With high correlation between ethical work environment and work engagement, this particular study tends to support the theoretical models proposed by Rothman (2017) Ethical Philosophical Constructs and Bakker’s (2011) Work Engagement Model.

Recommendations

This study recommends that:

1) Public HEIs in Sulu should continue enhancing their best practices in providing priority to employee rights, fair procedures, and equity in pay and promotion, and that promote tolerance, compassion, loyalty and honesty in the treatment of clientele and employees.

2) Administrators of public HEIs in Sulu should also continue enhancing their respective programs on ensuring their workers with high level of enthusiasm and dedication toward their jobs.

3) Moreover, student-researchers in the field of public administration are encouraged to conduct study similar to this one but to include other variables such as work performance and positions/ranks in some other settings.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents. Likewise, the anonymity of the respondents and the confidentiality of the data gathered from the respondents are safeguarded. The researcher also assures that plagiarism was strictly observed and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research

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